

Only eight varieties exhibited strong resistance to grain moth, with infestation restricted to only 0.8% of grains; five resistant varieties had damage of 1.1-2.4%.

R650-1820, Ratna/ARC19666 (IET11481), Ratna/ARC5981 (IET12805), Nagarjuna/ARC5984

(IET12785), and PR106/OBS528 had multiple resistance to BLB, BPH, and GM. They were resistant to GM biotype 1, with ARC10654, ARC5981, ARC5984, OBS528, and RP-9-4 as donors.

Varieties Ratna/ARC10654 (IET12770), Ratna/ARC10654

(IET12793), Ratna/ARC10654 (IET12206), R296-133, and R296-110 were also resistant to BPH and GM but moderately resistant or moderately susceptible to BLB. R650-1820 was the only variety resistant to BLB, BPH, GM, and grain moth infestation. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Analysis of bacterial blight resistance genes in three japonica rice varieties

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We analyzed inheritance of resistance to bacterial blight pathogen strains W1, P1 (PXO 61, Philippines), and T1 (Japan) in three japonica varieties (Ning 67, Tai 202, and Bing 814). Shennong 1033,

which is susceptible to these isolates, served as the susceptible parent. CBB3, CBB4, and CBB12, near-isogenic lines with resistance genes *Xa-3*, *Xa-4*, and *Xa-12*, respectively, are resistant to all of these isolates and served as the resistance parents. We made 12 crosses, including resistant/susceptible and resistant/resistant crosses (Tables 1 and 2).

All materials were planted in the field. Inoculum was adjusted to a concentration of 10^9 cells/ml. Fully expanded leaves at

booting stage were inoculated by the clipping method. A different tiller was inoculated with each isolate, and the tillers were marked with different colors. Disease reaction was assessed at 21 d after inoculation using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Plants scored as 1-3 were classified as resistant and those scored as 4-9 were classified as susceptible.

A single dominant gene controls the resistance of Ning 67 and Tai 202 to the three isolates and two dominant duplicate genes condition resistance in Bing 814 (Table 1). Allelism tests indicated that the genes of Ning 67 and Tai 202 were allelic to *Xa-3*, as was one of the two genes in Bing 814 (Table 2). ■

Table 1. Reactions of progeny of crosses among four parents to W1, P1, and T1 isolates of bacterial blight.

Parent or combination	Plants (no.)	RRR ^a	SSS ^a	Expected ratio	χ^2_c	P
Tai 202	13	13				
Ning 67	13	13				
Bing 814	14	14				
Shennong 1033	16		16			
Ning 67/Shennong 1033	F ₁ 14	14				
	F ₂ 209	164	45	3:1	1.1627	0.50-0.25
	B ₁ F ₁ 117	66	51	1:1	1.6752	0.50-0.25
Ning 67/Shennong 1033	F ₁ 13	13				
	F ₂ 208	165	43	3:1	1.8526	0.25-0.10
	B ₁ F ₁ 67	37	30	1:1	0.5373	0.50-0.25
Bing 814/Shennong 1033	F ₁ 12	12				
	F ₂ 206	191	15	15:1	0.2188	0.75-0.50
	B ₁ F ₁ 62	42	20	3:1	1.3763	0.25-0.10

^aThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to P1, and the third to T1.

Table 2. Segregation for resistance to W1, P1, and T1 isolates of crosses among three parents and known gene varieties.

Combination	F ₁	F ₂			Expected ratio	χ^2_c	P
		Total	RR	SS			
Ning 67/CBB3	RR ^a	209	209	0			
Ning 67/CBB4	RR ^b	116	109	7	15:1	0.0092	>0.90
Ning 67/CBB12	RR ^a	240	222	18	15:1	0.4444	0.75-0.50
Tai 202/CBB3	RR ^a	216	216	0			
Tai 202/CBB4	RR ^b	206	199	7	15:1	2.3935	0.25-0.10
Tai 202/CBB12	RR ^a	219	203	16	15:1	0.2560	0.75-0.50
Bing 814/CBB3	RR ^a	210	210	0			
Bing 814/CBB4	RR ^b	210	197	13	63:1	26.3114	<0.005
Bing 814/CBB12	RR ^a	197	192	5	63:1	0.6672	0.50-0.25

^aThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to T1. ^bThe first letter stands for reaction to W1, the second to P1.

Screening rice varieties for resistance to rice yellow mottle virus in Kenya

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We screened 60 rice varieties of diverse origins, supplied by IRRI, for their resistance to rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) during four seasons: 1989-91 long rains (LR) and 1989 short rains (SR). IR2793-80-1, which is grown commercially in western Kenya irrigation schemes, and local variety Sindano were included as checks.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design. The natural inoculation method was used. No pesticides were applied to facilitate the spread of the virus by beetles. Fertilizer was applied at 78 kg N/ha, half as basal and half at 42 DAT. Fields were kept clean with three hand weedings.

Test variety seedlings were sown at 20 × 20-cm spacing. Sindano, used as a

Average scores for reaction to RYMV at 90 DT of 60 varieties at AIRS, Kisumu, Kenya. 1989-91.

Variety	1989 LR ^a	1989 SR ^b	1990 LR ^a	1991 LR ^a	Av ^c	
Azucena	5	6	6	8	6.3	MS
Basmati 370	0	2	3	3	2	R
Basmati 217	0	2	3	3	2	R
BG35-2	7	7	5	7	6.5	S
BR51-282-8	7	8	7	8	7.5	S
BR153-2B-282-8	7	6	8	8	7.3	S
BRIRGA409	6	7	6	9	7	S
BW196	7	6	8	7	7	S
BW348-1	7	6	7	8	7	S
C1321-9	7	8	6	8	7.3	S
C1322-28	7	6	7	8	7	S
CR126-42-2	7	7	7	9	7.5	S
Elko	8	6	6	6	6.5	S
Faro 15	7	7	7	8	7.3	S
Faro 27	7	7	5	7	6.5	S
Farox 228-3-1-1	7	7	7	9	7.5	S
Farox 233-1-1-3	7	4	7	8	6.5	S
Farox 233-7-1-2	6	6	6	5	5.8	MS
Farox 239-1-1-1	7	6	5	7	6.3	S
IET6279	7	7	7	8	7.3	S
IR50	7	6	6	8	6.8	S
IR2793-80-1	5	6	6	9	6.5	S
IR9202-5-2-2-2	8	8	8	9	8.3	S
IR9698-16-3-2	6	6	8	7	6.8	S
IR9758-K2	8	6	5	8	6.8	S
IR9784-142-1-3-3	7	6	7	7	6.8	S
IR13260-100-1E-P2	6	6	8	7	6.8	S
IR19090-136-2-2-3	7	6	5	5	5.8	MS
IR19225-142-1-6	7	6	5	7	6.3	S
IR19225-289-3-1-3	8	8	6	7	7.3	S
IR24486-166-2-3	5	8	6	7	6.5	S
IR25873-22-3	7	6	5	8	6.5	S
IR27301-154-3	7	5	6	8	6.5	S
IR27301-62-2	7	7	7	8	7.3	S
ITA21	8	9	8	7	8	S
ITA222	7	8	5	8	7	S
ITA245	8	7	7	8	7.5	S
ITA249	5	6	7	9	6.8	S
ITA302	7	6	6	7	6.5	S
ITA310	4	6	3	8	5.3	MS
JC99	7	7	8	9	7.8	S
K39-96-1-1-1-2	7	7	6	8	7	S
K143-1-2	4	6	3	9	5.5	MS
KAU166	6	6	3	7	5.5	MS
Ketan1	5	4	4	3	4	MR
Kisuke	2	0	2	2	1.5	R
Khao Dawk Mall	3	0	3	3	2.3	R
Malagkit Sungsong	4	4	4	4	4	MR
Milyang 49	6	6	7	8	6.8	S
RP1125-1526-2-2-3	5	5	5	7	5.5	MS
Shin-al	7	5	4	5	5.3	MS
Sindano	9	9	9	9	9	HS
SI-PI-692033	8	7	6	8	7.3	S
TNAU658	7	8	5	8	7	S
TOX714-1-204-1-101	7	7	6	6	6.3	S
TOX902-42-1	6	4	6	7	5.8	MS
TOX902-5-103-3-101	7	6	5	8	6.5	S
TOX894-28-201-1-5	8	6	5	8	6.8	S
TOX894-28-201-1-2	8	9	6	8	7.8	S
UPR254-35-3-2	5	6	6	8	6.3	S
Total	378	365	350	431		
Mean	6	6	6	7		
F-test for variety comparison		0.29 %				
CV		16 %				
SED		0.7 %				
LSD (5%)		1.4 %				
LSD (1%)		1.9 %				

^aLR = long rainy season. ^bSR = short rainy season. ^cR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

spreader variety, was planted at 60- × 20-cm spacing. The test varieties were transplanted in three rows inside the Sindano rows at 21 d after sowing. Plants were inoculated at 18 d after transplanting (DT).

A mixture of 100 g infected leaves ground in 1 liter of distilled water with 5 ml of a phosphate buffer (to maintain pH 7.0) and 2 g of a carborundum powder (an abrasive) was used to inoculate the Sindano plants. The finger rubber technique was used, where fingers are dipped in the inoculum and then rubbed gently on all of the plants' leaves two to three times. RYMV symptoms were scored systematically using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* at 42 DT, 56 DT, 70 DT, and 90 DT.

Ketan 1 and Malagkit Sungsong were moderately resistant while Basmati 370, Basmati 217, Kisuke, and Khao Dawk Mali were resistant (see table). Nine varieties were moderately susceptible. Sindano was highly susceptible. ■

Identifying resistance genes for bacterial blight in Chengte 232

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We analyzed the bacterial blight resistance genes and their allelism for Chengte 232 and its resistance donors, using the pathogen strains W1, P1 (PXO 61, Philippines), and T1 (Japan). Chengte 232 and its resistant donors, Nongken 58 and Hongkewan, were all resistant to the three isolates; its other donor, Tetep, was resistant to T1 but susceptible to W1 and P1. Near-isogenic lines carrying known genes, CBB3(*Xa-3*) and CBB4(*Xa-4*), were resistant to these isolates. Nonghu 6, which is susceptible to the isolates, served as the susceptible parent.

To determine the number of resistance genes effective against the isolates tested, Chengte 232, Nongken 58, and Tetep were each crossed with Nonghu 6. We also crossed Chengte 232 with Tetep and Nongken 58, and Chengte 232 and Nongken 58 with CBB3 and CBB4 to test allelism of resistance genes.